

REVIEW

<https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-026-06760-9>

OPEN

A bibliometric analysis of the impact of climate change on immovable cultural heritage employing Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

Ionut Cristi Nicu^{1✉}, Athos Agapiou² & Paloma Guzman¹

This study presents the first large-scale bibliometric analysis of academic research applying Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to explore the relationship between climate change and immovable cultural heritage. Drawing on 82 English-language publications indexed in the Web of Science Core Collection (1994–2024), the study maps the field’s evolution over the past three decades. Results show a steady increase in publications and citations, reflecting the growing importance of GIS as a methodological bridge linking environmental sciences, geosciences, and heritage management. Research has primarily focused on climate risk assessment (CRA), particularly hazard, exposure, and vulnerability mapping, while studies addressing adaptation planning or governance remain limited. The prominence of environmental and geoscientific disciplines underscores strong technical foundations, yet collaboration across social and policy domains remains fragmented. The relatively modest use of AI-based modelling and remote sensing also points to untapped potential for technological innovation. Overall, the findings indicate a rapidly expanding but still consolidating research landscape and highlight the need for greater interdisciplinarity, interoperable data infrastructures, and integrative approaches to support evidence-based heritage management and climate adaptation.

Introduction

Cultural heritage encompasses both tangible and intangible dimensions that shape how societies interact with their environments. Tangible heritage (such as buildings, monuments, and cultural landscapes) embodies material evidence of human creativity and adaptation to local conditions, while intangible attributes (such as knowledge systems, practices, and meanings) sustain the cultural values that give these places their significance (UNESCO 2023). Together, these dimensions form interdependent socio-ecological systems in which environmental processes and cultural practices co-evolve. Within this continuum, immovable cultural heritage, the focus of this study, materializes how societies have historically negotiated environmental change (Bucci 2018).

Understanding immovable heritage as part of broader landscape systems extends its relevance from site conservation to spatial planning and policy. Heritage assets are embedded within

¹Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research, Oslo, Norway. ²Cyprus University of Technology, Limassol, Cyprus. ✉email: ionut.cristi.nicu@niku.no

multi-scalar territorial networks where ecological and social processes intersect (Kutut et al. 2021). This perspective situates heritage within the landscape–planning nexus (Guzman and Daly 2025), highlighting its role in informing adaptation frameworks that integrate spatial, environmental, and cultural dimensions (Biesbroek et al. 2025; López Sánchez et al. 2020).

Climate change amplifies pressures on heritage through rising temperatures, altered precipitation, sea-level rise, and extreme events, resulting in material decay, landscape transformation, and the erosion of cultural practices (Abounaga et al. 2024; Sesana et al. 2021). These effects are documented across a range of climatic regions, from arid (Salameh and Touqan, 2023), and Mediterranean (Kapsomenakis et al. 2022), to temperate (Cacciotti et al. 2021; Nicu, 2017), and Arctic contexts (Nicu et al. 2025; Nicu et al. 2022), revealing the global exposure of immovable heritage (Afroz, 2024). At the same time, heritage embodies cumulative knowledge of environmental management. Construction materials, water systems, and settlement patterns reflect centuries of adaptation to climatic variability, offering insights relevant to contemporary resilience planning (Javaid et al. 2024; Vilcea et al. 2023).

Policy frameworks have gradually evolved to acknowledge this dual role of heritage—as a domain exposed to risk and a source of knowledge for adaptation. The 2017 ICOMOS Triennial General Assembly and the Climate Change and Heritage Working Group underscored that heritage must be integrated into climate policy, both as a vulnerable resource and a repository of adaptive practice (ICOMOS 2017; ICOMOS 2019). The International Co-Sponsored Meeting on Culture, Heritage, and Climate Change further advanced this perspective, promoting collaboration between scientists, local communities, and Indigenous peoples to combine data-driven and experiential knowledge (Hub 2024). Within Europe, the EU Work Plan for Culture 2023–2026 situates heritage as a source of transferable practices for strengthening resilience (Pasikowska-Schnass 2024).

At the global level, the Conference of the Parties (COP) processes and the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA) highlight the need for consistent measures and interoperable datasets to assess adaptation progress across sectors, including heritage (Adaptation 2024). Yet, while international tracking often relies on national statistics and aggregated indices, such data rarely capture the complexity of local contexts or the relational nature of heritage values. The challenge lies in developing multi-scalar measures and spatial datasets that reflect both material and cultural dimensions of vulnerability and adaptation (Biesbroek et al. 2025). Addressing this gap requires tools capable of integrating diverse forms of evidence and linking site-based observations with territorial assessments.

Against this backdrop, Geographic Information Systems (GIS) provide essential tools for documenting, analysing, and monitoring cultural heritage in a changing climate. Their ability to combine multi-source datasets, from spatially gridded climate models to on-site observations, makes them central to identifying exposure, assessing risk in heritage structures, and supporting adaptation planning (Agapiou and Skarlatos 2023; Luo et al. 2023). However, a key methodological challenge lies in merging quantitative data, such as hazard modelling or geophysical mapping, with qualitative and historical information that reflects cultural values and social dynamics. Bridging these domains requires developing approaches that transform qualitative, value-based information into spatially interpretable formats to inform decision-making (Doyle et al. 2019). Advances in remote sensing, participatory mapping, and artificial-intelligence-based analysis are beginning to address these gaps, but their integration into heritage adaptation studies remains limited (Liu et al. 2024). Strengthening the relationship between quantitative and

qualitative information represents a critical frontier for using GIS to advance systemic, multi-scalar approaches to climate adaptation in heritage contexts (López-González et al. 2022; Quamar et al. 2023).

Despite the growing interest in applying GIS to cultural heritage conservation and management, academic research on this topic remains in its early stages, fragmented across disciplines and lacking comprehensive synthesis. Existing reviews have explored related areas, including bibliometric analyses of GIS applications in heritage studies (Huang 2024), cultural heritage research in the humanities (Vlase and Lahdesmaki 2023), climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage in polar regions (Nicu and Fatorić 2023), and heritage visualisation using Web of Science (Tang et al. 2024). However, no study to date has systematically examined the intersection of climate change, immovable cultural heritage, and GIS. The original contribution of this review lies in the use of bibliometrics to systematically map, for the first time, the specific intersection of climate change, immovable cultural heritage, and GIS. Existing bibliometric work either treats GIS in heritage in general, or climate and heritage without a dedicated focus on spatial technologies, so they cannot reveal how GIS-based climate research on immovable heritage has actually developed as a distinct domain. To address this gap, this study conducts a bibliometric analysis of academic literature exploring the intersection of GIS, cultural heritage, and climate change. The study aims to: (1) to map how this research field evolved over time, identifying the main scientific communities and methods; (2) to identify influential publications, authors, and journals, as well as thematic clusters and gaps, that structure current knowledge on GIS-based assessments of climate risks to heritage; and (3) to translate these patterns into policy-relevant insights, showing how existing research supports – or fails to support – the data needs of international and national climate adaptation frameworks, and where future work should focus to better inform monitoring, planning and decision-making.

Data and methodology

Data source and search strategy. The systematic literature review involved the structured selection and analysis of academic publications retrieved from the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection, following clearly defined inclusion criteria (Berrang-Ford et al. 2011; Petticrew and Roberts 2006). WoS was chosen as the data source due to its extensive coverage across multiple disciplines relevant to this study—environmental sciences, geosciences, archaeology, and planning—and for its robust citation indexing capabilities, which support comparative bibliometric mapping (Gusenbauer and Haddaway 2020).

The search strategy combined seven query strings incorporating the terms *climate*, *heritage*, and *GIS* (Table 1). The set of seven queries has been deliberately structured to capture all relevant literature on the impacts of climate change on immovable cultural heritage using GIS, while minimising irrelevant results. Each term combination is designed to target a

Query no	Query	Results
Q1	climat* AND cultural heritag* AND GIS	91
Q2	climat* AND heritag* site AND GIS	81
Q3	climat* AND cultural feat* AND GIS	48
Q4	climat* AND archaeol* site AND GIS	115
Q5	climat* AND historic* site AND GIS	152
Q6	climat* AND cultural resource AND GIS	68
Q7	climat* AND archaeol* resource AND GIS	29
	Total	584

Table 2 Information extracted from WOS engine.

No	Information extracted from WOS
1.	Author(s)
2.	Document title
3.	Year
4.	EID (Scopus Electronic Identifier)
5.	Source title
6.	Volume, issues, pages
7.	Citation count
8.	Source and document type
9.	Publication stage
10.	DOI
11.	Open access
12.	Affiliations
13.	Publisher
14.	Language of original document
15.	Abstract
16.	Author keywords
17.	Indexed keywords

specific strand of terminology that is commonly used in heritage and GIS scholarship and policy documents (Orr et al. 2021). All queries use “climat” and “GIS” as mandatory components to restrict results to climate-change-related studies that explicitly employ Geographic Information Systems. The categorisation of heritage terms can be divided into three main categories, as outlined in the systematic reviews of climate change and cultural heritage, as well as in GIS/cultural resource literature: (a) generic heritage terms (cultural heritage, heritage site, cultural feature), (b) discipline-specific labels (archaeological site/resource), and (c) management/planning terminology (historic site, cultural resource). Consequently, the objective of the present study is to comprehensively encompass the practical vocabulary employed in the context of immovable cultural heritage in GIS-based climate-impact research, whilst maintaining specificity to the exclusion of literature pertaining to intangible heritage or non-spatial climate studies. Queries were applied to the Topic field, which includes title, abstract, and author keywords, and the search was performed on 31 October 2024. The initial dataset comprised 584 records, of which 521 were journal articles and the remainder conference papers or book chapters.

Data extraction and cleaning. All retrieved records were exported from WoS in .csv, .txt and .ris formats for subsequent processing. Duplicates across the seven queries were automatically identified through bibliographic matching and removed. The exported data contained 17 bibliographic and citation fields used for analysis, including author, title, year, source title, citation count, affiliations, keywords, and document type (Table 2). These metadata fields enabled the examination of publication patterns, collaboration networks, and thematic trends across the dataset.

The resulting dataset of 354 unique publications was then screened for thematic relevance to the study’s focus on climate change, immovable cultural heritage, and GIS. Two of the study’s authors independently reviewed the abstracts to ensure alignment with these themes. The review process followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) protocol (Page et al. 2022) to ensure transparency and reproducibility. Inter-rater reliability between reviewers was calculated at 97.7%, following established procedures for coding consistency. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion, resulting in a final selection of 82 publications (see Supplementary Material 1) for detailed analysis (Table 3).

Table 3 Cross comparison of the remaining articles by the first and second authors.

Step 1: Individual review			
	Author 1	Author 2	
Accepted	88	83	
Excluded	266	260	
Step 2: Comparison of the individual reviews			
Same decision	346 (97.7%)		
Different decision	8 (2.3%)		
Step 3: Discussions for the individual reviews			
Approved after joint discussions	3		
Rejected after joint discussions	5		
Step 4: Final list of papers			
Total papers for further review	82		

Bibliometric approach and analytical tools. Bibliometric analysis, which quantitatively evaluates publication patterns, offers a valuable approach to identify key research areas, influential works, emerging themes, and knowledge gaps within the literature (Huang 2024; Tang et al. 2024; Vlase and Lahdesmaki 2023). This method provides a systematic and replicable way to analyse a large body of research and to reveal the intellectual structure and evolution of a field. Bibliometric and network analyses were performed using a combination of tools: WoS “Analyze Results” and “Citation Reports” functions to generate descriptive statistics on publication output, document types, and citation trends; VOSviewer 1.6.19 (van Eck and Waltman 2010) for co-authorship and keyword co-occurrence analyses visualising collaboration patterns among authors, institutions, and countries; and CiteSpace (Chen 2005) to detect temporal trends, keyword clusters, and citation bursts. This integrated analytical workflow provided both quantitative and relational insights into the structure and evolution of research addressing climate change, immovable cultural heritage, and GIS.

Data selection and validation. The selection process ensured that only peer-reviewed works explicitly linking GIS applications, cultural heritage, and climate change impacts were retained. Publications focusing exclusively on remote sensing without a cultural heritage component, or on heritage unrelated to climate dynamics, were excluded. Each selected article was examined to verify its methodological relevance, ensuring consistency across spatial, technological, and thematic dimensions. To enhance data transparency, all bibliographic information used in this analysis was obtained from publicly available WoS records. The dataset and corresponding metadata can be made available upon reasonable request for verification or further analysis.

Analytical framework. The final dataset was analysed to identify (1) temporal trends in publication activity; (2) the most productive countries, institutions, and journals; (3) the evolution of research themes through keyword co-occurrence; and (4) collaboration networks among authors. These analyses collectively reveal the dynamics and emerging directions of research at the intersection of climate change, GIS, and immovable cultural heritage. The results are presented in the next section.

Results

Temporal distribution of publications. The temporal analysis of the 82 selected publications shows that research on climate change and immovable cultural heritage using GIS began to appear in the mid-1990s, with a marked increase after 2014. No publications were recorded before 1994. The number of studies grew steadily over the last decade (2014–2024), during which 77

Fig. 1 Temporal distribution of publications and citations (1994–2024) on climate change, immovable cultural heritage, and GIS. Source: Citation Report based on WOS list of indexed articles 1994–2024 on the topic of “climat* AND cultural heritag* AND GIS”, “climat* AND heritag* site AND GIS”, “climat* AND cultural feat* AND GIS”, “climat* AND archaeol* site AND GIS”, “climat* AND historic* site AND GIS”, “climat* AND cultural resource AND GIS”, “climat* AND archaeol* resource AND GIS”. N = 82. Articles indexed in by 31 October 2024.

papers (93%) of the total dataset were published. Citation activity followed a similar pattern, rising from five citations in 2015 to 302 in 2023, reflecting growing academic interest in the topic (Fig. 1).

Scientific fields and research categories. The classification of the 82 selected publications within the WoS categories shows that research on climate change and immovable cultural heritage using GIS is distributed across two main tiers of scientific fields. The first tier includes high-frequency categories that dominate the dataset, while the second tier comprises complementary disciplines that contribute to its interdisciplinary character (Table 4).

The first tier of research categories includes *Environmental Sciences*, *Geosciences* (Multidisciplinary), and *Archaeology*, which together account for almost 90% of all publications. These categories encompass studies assessing the physical and geomorphological impacts of climate change on cultural landscapes and archaeological sites, often through GIS-based modelling and spatial analysis. Examples include investigations of coastal erosion and site retreat (Ackland et al. 2023; Asăndulesei et al. 2020), flood-risk mapping for historical settlements (Dimitriou 2022; Howard et al. 2017), and analyses of sea-level-rise exposure for low-lying heritage zones (Hil, 2019; Li et al. 2022). Other research applies GIS to quantify vulnerability across multiple hazards, integrating geotechnical, climatic, and spatial indicators (Gizzi et al. 2016; Nicu et al. 2021).

The second tier comprises *Water Resources*, *Environmental Studies*, *Remote Sensing*, and other fields related to Earth observation, urban planning, and risk assessment. Typical examples involve the use of satellite and UAV data for mapping changes in coastal and fluvial heritage environments (Usmanov et al. 2018; Westley and McNeary 2015) and applications of multi-criteria analysis and remote-sensing imagery to assess site vulnerability (Kittipongvises et al. 2020; Rodriguez-Rosales et al. 2021). These results show that the research domain operates

Table 4 Distribution of Top 10 publications by research category according to the WoS classification.

Research areas (WOS categories)	Record count	% of 82
Environmental sciences	25	30.48
Geosciences multidisciplinary	25	30.48
Archaeology	22	26.82
Water resources	16	19.51
Environmental studies	14	17.07
Meteorology atmospheric sciences	12	14.63
Materials science multidisciplinary	11	13.41
Art	8	9.75
Chemistry analytical	8	9.75
Green sustainable science technology	8	9.75

primarily at the interface of environmental and geoscientific disciplines, with archaeology providing a significant applied dimension to heritage-specific analyses.

Countries and institutions. The geographic distribution of publications highlights contributions from a limited number of countries and institutions (Tables 5 and 6). The most representative countries are China, Italy, United Kingdom, and United States, followed by Greece, Romania, and Norway. Together, these countries account for more than two-thirds of the total publications.

At the institutional level, 150 organisations were identified, though only a small group, led by the *Chinese Academy of Sciences*, *National Research Council of Italy (CNR)*, and *University of Cambridge*, produced three or more papers each. The majority of institutions contributed single publications, indicating a wide but shallow participation across organisations.

Publishing journals and articles. The 82 publications are distributed across a diverse range of interdisciplinary journals (Fig.

Table 5 Top 10 countries publishing on climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage using GIS.

Countries	Record count	% of 82
Italy	14	17.07
China	11	13.41
England	9	10.97
Spain	8	9.75
Australia	7	8.53
USA	7	8.53
Greece	5	6.09
Germany	4	4.87
Japan	4	4.87
Austria	3	3.65

Source: Authors based on WOS queries using “Analyze Results” tool on the saved list of $N = 82$ articles on climate change effects on immovable cultural heritage using GIS indexed in WOS.

Table 6 Top 10 most productive institutions by number of articles publishing on climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage using GIS.

Institutions	Record count	% of 82
Chinese Academy of Sciences	3	3.65
Newcastle University UK	3	3.65
Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research NIKU	3	3.65
Polytechnic University of Milan	3	3.65
Universidad Pablo de Olavide	3	3.65
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences CAS	3	3.65
University of Sevilla	3	3.65
Alexandru Ioan Cuza University	2	2.43
Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique CNRS	2	2.43
Centro Euro Mediterraneo sui Cambimenti Climatici CMCC	2	2.43

Source: Authors based on WOS queries using “Analyze Results” tool on the saved list of $N = 82$ articles on climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage using GIS indexed in WOS.

Fig. 2 Top publishing journals by the number of papers published in the field of climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage using GIS between 1994 and 2024.

2). The highest number of papers ($n = 8$) was published in the *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, followed by *Land* ($n = 5$), *Sustainability* ($n = 4$), and the *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction* ($n = 4$). Other relevant journals include *Water* and the *Journal of Island and Coastal Archaeology* (three papers each), as well as *Science of the Total Environment*, *ISPRS International*

Journal of Geo-Information, *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, *Applied Geomatics*, and *Natural Hazards* (two papers each). The remaining publications appear as individual articles across a wider set of outlets, including conference proceedings and book chapters.

The analysis of citation frequency across the dataset identified the most influential works based on their total citation counts in the Web of Science database (Table 7).

Co-authorship networks. Co-authorship analysis based on the 82 publications identified a total of 353 co-authors affiliated with 150 institutions. Using VOSviewer, two main collaboration clusters were detected, each representing groups of researchers working primarily within regional or institutional networks (Figs. 3 and 4).

The number of papers per author remains low, with a maximum of two publications per individual, and the average number of co-authors per article is 4.3. Institutional collaboration follows a similar pattern: only a few universities or research centres appear in more than one publication, while most are represented once. These results indicate limited cross-institutional collaboration within the field.

Keywords analysis and research themes. Keyword co-occurrence analysis was conducted using VOSviewer, generating a network of the most frequently used author keywords (Fig. 5).

The analysis identified *GIS* as the most prominent keyword (mentioned 25 times), followed by *climate change* (20 occurrences) and *cultural heritage* (16 occurrences). Other recurrent terms include *remote sensing* (6), *risk* (5), *vulnerability* (4), *adaptation* (4), and *archaeological sites* (4). The co-occurrence structure shows that research in this field primarily focuses on the spatial analysis of climate impacts and risk assessment for cultural heritage, often integrating environmental and archaeological dimensions.

Four main thematic clusters can be distinguished within the keyword network. The first cluster focuses on climate-induced physical processes affecting heritage, including studies on coastal erosion and shoreline retreat (Ackland et al. 2023; Asăndulesei et al. 2020) and soil or slope instability (Jiao et al. 2019; Kim and Kim 2021). The second cluster revolves around risk and vulnerability mapping, frequently applying multi-criteria and analytical hierarchy processes to rank threats or prioritise conservation zones (Gizzi et al. 2016; Kittipongvises et al. 2020; Lei et al. 2023).

A third cluster groups research employing remote sensing and monitoring techniques for documentation and change detection in heritage landscapes (Hil 2019; Rodriguez-Rosales et al. 2021; Usmanov et al. 2018; Westley and McNeary 2015). These studies often merge satellite or UAV imagery with GIS modelling to detect degradation patterns and assess exposure to sea-level rise or flooding. The fourth cluster encompasses adaptation and management perspectives, which are less numerous but expanding, addressing the use of GIS to support planning and decision-making for at-risk cultural sites (Nicu et al. 2022; Ravankhah et al. 2020). Overall, the keyword network reflects a research domain primarily oriented toward quantitative spatial assessment of risk, with emerging links to adaptation, management, and resilience planning.

Temporal and thematic trends. Keyword evolution analysis performed in CiteSpace provided insight into the temporal dynamics of the field between 2020 and 2023 (Figs. 6 and 7). This analysis has revealed a congruence with preceding studies, whilst concurrently offering unique insights by identifying rapidly emerging themes or “keywords”. This was facilitated by a burst-

Table 7 The most cited articles on climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage using GIS.

Authors	Article title	Journal title	No. of citations
Kittipongvises et al. (2020)	AHP-GIS analysis for flood hazard assessment of the communities nearby the world heritage site on Ayutthaya Island, Thailand	<i>International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction</i>	90
Saha et al. (2021)	Modelling multi-hazard threats to cultural heritage sites and environmental sustainability: The present and future scenarios	<i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i>	63
Ortiz et al. (2014)	Approach to environmental risk analysis for the main monuments in a historical city	<i>Journal of Cultural Heritage</i>	60
Jiao et al. (2019)	Performance evaluation for four GIS-based models purposed to predict and map landslide susceptibility: A case study at a World Heritage site in Southwest China	<i>CATENA</i>	54
Sardella et al. (2020)	Risk Mapping for the Sustainable Protection of Cultural Heritage in Extreme Changing Environments	<i>Atmosphere</i>	47
Ravankhah et al. (2019)	Integrated Assessment of Natural Hazards, Including Climate Change's Influences, for Cultural Heritage Sites: The Case of the Historic Centre of Rethymno in Greece	<i>International Journal of Disaster Risk Science</i>	47
Cacciotti et al. (2021)	Climate change-induced disasters and cultural heritage: Optimizing management strategies in Central Europe	<i>Climate Risk Management</i>	43
Hategekimana et al. (2018)	Integration of multi-parametric fuzzy analytic hierarchy process and GIS along the UNESCO World Heritage: a flood hazard index, Mombasa County, Kenya	<i>Natural Hazards</i>	41
Ronco et al. (2014)	The KULTURisk Regional Risk Assessment methodology for water-related natural hazards - Part 1: Physical-environmental assessment	<i>Hydrology and Earth System Sciences</i>	41
Taromideh et al. (2022)	Urban Flood-Risk Assessment: Integration of Decision-Making and Machine Learning	<i>Sustainability</i>	39

Fig. 3 Co-authorship network visualisation based on author unit of analysis. Minimum number of papers per author $n = 2$, number of institutions meeting this threshold $n = 353$. The authors represented in the map $n = 5$ have no link strength and are grouped in five different clusters).

detection algorithm embedded within CiteSpace, a software specifically designed to identify novel and significant concepts within the research landscape.

As illustrated in Fig. 6, there has been a shift in the geographical distribution of research focus, with leading regions and institutions emerging in different locations. For instance, in 2020 (Fig. 6a), studies conducted primarily by Canadian researchers focused on the Arctic (Walls et al. 2020), particularly on permafrost thaw and its subsequent impact on the development of thaw slumps affecting immovable cultural heritage of the Arctic. Permafrost thaw is regarded as a direct consequence of climate change (Rantanen et al. 2022). Conversely, in 2021 (Fig. 6b), the focus shifted to modelling soil erosion under different future climate and land use change, with notable contributions from Indian institutions (Saha et al. 2021). In 2022, most of the research concentrated on climate change and vulnerability, with China (Fig. 6c) dominating the latter (Li et al. 2022). In 2023, however, there was a diversification of methods, with the use of

Fig. 4 Co-authorship analysis at institution level. Minimum number of papers per institution $n = 3$, number of institutions meeting this threshold $n = 176$. The institutions represented in the map $n = 6$ have no link strength and are grouped in six different clusters).

Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Fig. 6d) to assess the impacts of climate change on immovable cultural heritage employing GIS (Quesada-Ganuza et al. 2023).

A more detailed visual representation of the evolution of the scientific landscape over time is presented in Fig. 7, based on the analysis of authors and keywords. The various clusters are represented by horizontal lines throughout the period from 2009 to 2024, thereby highlighting the main research themes and their interconnections. The nodes in the visualisation represent pivotal concepts or research topics, with larger nodes denoting more significant or frequently cited topics. The colour coding of the nodes reflects a temporal progression, with earlier topics indicated by blue or purple (from ~2009) and newer topics shown in red or pink (up to 2024).

Fig. 5 Map of trending topics according to the authors' keywords in analysed publications.

Fig. 6 Temporal evolution of keyword co-occurrence networks in research on climate impacts to cultural heritage employing GIS. Frequency burst based on keywords for the year 2020 (a), 2021 (b), 2022 (c) and 2023 (d).

An interesting topic that has emerged (around 2020) in two clusters—namely, climate change and climate damage assessment—relates to the coastal environment and how this specific zone is affected by climate change. Similar trends have been observed in studies related to flooding (c. 2021). From a broader perspective, this shift indicates that, in recent years, research has moved from broader themes (e.g., natural hazards, vulnerability) to more targeted studies focusing on specific research themes. This trend highlights the growing need for in-depth studies addressing various aspects of climate change.

The edges (lines) connecting the nodes in Fig. 7 represent the relationships between the concepts, including co-citations and thematic links in research papers. The thickness of the lines indicates the strength of the connection between topics, with thicker lines denoting stronger or more frequent associations. The colour of the edges reflects the timeline, illustrating how the

connections between these concepts have evolved over time, with clusters of nodes, which are labelled with key terms such as “cultural heritage,” “climate change,” and “vulnerabilities,” indicating distinct areas of research. The size of the text corresponds to the prominence of the theme within the field with larger text denoting more influential or widely studied topics. The proximity of terms within clusters such as “sea level rise”, “erosion” and “coastal archaeology”, highlights closely related areas of research that frequently co-occur in academic studies.

It is noteworthy that key themes (clusters) such as “climate change” and “cultural heritage” underscore the field’s primary focus on preserving heritage against environmental threats. The adaptation and vulnerability clusters highlight efforts to evaluate the risks posed to heritage sites by natural hazards. GIS platforms can play a pivotal role in spatial risk analysis and the development

Fig. 7 Temporal evolution of the scientific field of climate change effects on cultural heritage employing GIS (Line thickness indicates the strength of connections between topics, while colour reflects the timeline, showing the evolution of these associations. Key clusters, labelled with terms like “cultural heritage” and “climate change” represent distinct research areas. Text size denotes the prominence of each theme, with larger text highlighting more influential or frequently studied topics).

of adaptation strategies and policy recommendations. Clusters focused on “coastal erosion” and “remote sensing” underscore targeted research for vulnerable coastal regions, utilizing GIS and satellite technologies to monitor and address site degradation. Meanwhile, the “risk assessment” and “management cluster” reflect an applied (Hub) approach, aiming to establish frameworks for the proactive management of heritage structures at risk. Collectively, these clusters demonstrate a multidisciplinary and technologically advanced field that integrates both methodological and geographical perspectives to support heritage conservation in an era of environmental change.

A particularly valuable feature of this analysis is the burst detection, which is represented by pink diamonds around certain nodes (Fig. 7). These diamonds identify terms or concepts that have recently surged in popularity. For example, terms such as “climate change” and “cultural heritage” have seen a notable increase in attention in recent years. This visualization provides insight into the dynamic nature of the field, mapping both longstanding topics and emerging trends. However, the chronological representation may present certain limitations, such as the risk of oversimplifying the connections between themes and potentially underrepresenting the multi-disciplinary nature of this research, particularly in fields like landscape studies that integrate diverse methodologies and perspectives. This can be also linked with the relevant small number of studies examined in this study (82 papers). Further analysis of why certain themes (clusters) is more tightly linked could provide deeper insights; for instance, connections may be strengthened by shared methodologies (e.g., remote sensing), specific regional studies, or collaborative networks, i.e., research groups that systematically collaborate for specific studies. Understanding emerging topics can offer an indication into (near) future directions of the field, highlighting potential research gaps, such as underexplored geographic areas

or underutilized methods and topics that need to be further addressed. A comparison of themes from around 2010 with recent ones sheds light on shifts in research paradigms. These shifts may be driven by evolving tools, data availability, new methodologies and a growing awareness of the relation and impact of climate change on heritage sites. These shifts not only reflect a changing rationale within the field but also suggest new opportunities for advancing conservation strategies and expanding interdisciplinary collaboration.

Discussion

Research development and maturity. The bibliometric analysis reveals that research on climate change and immovable cultural heritage using GIS has expanded substantially since 2014, with a steady increase in both publications and citations. This growth reflects the growing recognition of cultural heritage within the broader climate adaptation and environmental management research agendas. The predominance of publications in the last decade, coupled with concentration in geoscientific and ecological fields, suggests that the field is still consolidating. Research remains focused mainly on physical processes—such as erosion, flooding, and sea-level rise—documented through GIS-based risk mapping, while only a limited number of studies advance towards adaptation and management frameworks (Nicu et al. 2022; Ravankhah et al. 2020).

The concentration of outputs within *Environmental Sciences*, *Geosciences Multidisciplinary*, and *Archaeology* illustrates the dominance of natural science-oriented perspectives, often focusing on physical processes, spatial analysis, and site-based vulnerability. While this demonstrates a solid methodological foundation, it also indicates that heritage-focused research on adaptation and resilience remains underrepresented in comparison to the technical modelling dimension. The absence of major

thematic bursts in keyword evolution suggests a stable yet still maturing research field, where methodological refinement currently outweighs conceptual diversification.

Interdisciplinarity, scale, and systemic understanding. The results demonstrate an uneven disciplinary structure: while environmental and geoscientific approaches provide quantitative insights into exposure and risk, social, cultural, and governance dimensions are less systematically integrated. This asymmetry limits GIS-based research's capacity to capture the relational and value-based dimensions of cultural heritage fully. A key challenge is the issue of scale. Much of the data analysed in this research area comes from national or global datasets, which, while comprehensive, often hide local differences and site-specific heritage traits. On the other hand, locally focused studies, especially those dealing with adaptation or management, are seldom included in larger-scale analyses. Fixing this multi-scalar disconnect is crucial to develop systems that link territorial planning, heritage preservation, and climate adaptation. GIS and related geospatial technologies have great potential to close these gaps. They enable the integration of diverse datasets and the multi-layered analysis of environmental, spatial, and socio-cultural information. However, the results also indicate that more methodological innovation is needed to combine quantitative data (such as hazard models and exposure maps) with qualitative and historical knowledge, which are essential for understanding heritage values and local responses. Improving this connection can enhance GIS-based approaches' ability to support adaptive planning and evidence-based heritage management.

Emerging research themes and methodological gaps. Across the corpus, research converges on several recurring themes: spatial documentation of risk, vulnerability mapping, coastal and archaeological site monitoring, and applications of remote sensing for heritage protection. These cases highlight how local perspectives can complement scientific datasets and provide a finer spatial understanding of cultural values and climate risks. Such examples, though rare, illustrate the potential for merging qualitative insights with quantitative geospatial frameworks. Although the majority of studies focus on quantitative modelling and physical risk mapping, a small subset of publications explores the integration of traditional and Indigenous knowledge with scientific data to inform local adaptation strategies. Examples include participatory mapping and community-based approaches applied in the Solomon Islands (Leon et al. 2015) and on the Pamunkey Indian Reservation in the United States (Hutton and Allen 2020). These studies demonstrate how local knowledge can complement geospatial analysis by providing historical and experiential insights into climate impacts, risk perception, and site-level adaptation priorities. Despite their limited representation in the corpus, such approaches underscore the potential for more inclusive, socially grounded applications of GIS in heritage-related climate research. Methodologically, the results underscore the need for interoperable datasets and harmonised metadata structures that can link heritage information systems with environmental and policy data repositories. This would enhance cross-sectoral collaboration and improve comparability between studies. Integrating participatory GIS, cultural mapping, and AI-assisted document analysis may further advance the representation of intangible and value-based information within spatial datasets.

Policy implications and recommendations. The findings carry several implications for advancing the integration of cultural heritage into climate adaptation policy. Despite the increasing

acknowledgment of heritage within global frameworks—such as the ICOMOS Triennial General Assembly (2017), the International Co-Sponsored Meeting on Culture, Heritage, and Climate Change (2024), and the EU Work Plan for Culture 2023–2026, the bibliometric evidence shows that this recognition has not yet translated into coherent research agendas or cross-sectoral implementation frameworks. The persistence of disciplinary silos between heritage management, environmental sciences, and spatial planning continues to limit the capacity to operationalize heritage within adaptation monitoring and decision-making.

A first implication concerns the urgent need to strengthen data infrastructures that link cultural heritage inventories with climate-related datasets. Interoperable platforms that combine geospatial, environmental, and cultural data would enable consistent tracking of risks and adaptation measures across scales, from the local site to national adaptation reporting. Such infrastructures could also support the development of shared metrics for assessing climate impacts on heritage, thereby aligning with the objectives of the Global Goal on Adaptation (GGA) and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction.

A second implication concerns cross-sector collaboration and capacity building. The results show that most research focuses on technical areas, while the social, institutional, and policy aspects of heritage adaptation are less developed. Therefore, increased cooperation among environmental scientists, heritage professionals, and planners is crucial. Joint training programs and interdisciplinary funding initiatives could promote better understanding of heritage values, risk management, and adaptation strategies, emphasizing culture's role as both a resource and a catalyst for climate resilience.

Finally, a more coordinated policy approach should aim to harmonize methodologies and governance tools that define adaptation within the heritage sector. Integrating GIS-based evidence and spatial risk modelling with planning and conservation policies would help bridge the current divide between research outputs and decision-making processes. Studies applying these approaches—for instance, in flood-risk management for historical centres (Ravankhah et al. 2020) and vulnerability assessment frameworks for cultural landscapes (Cacciotti et al. 2021)—demonstrate the feasibility of aligning geospatial data with adaptive governance instruments. Policymakers can build on such examples by embedding harmonised methodologies into national adaptation plans and cultural heritage strategies, ensuring that data-driven insights inform territorial and sectoral policies alike. Aligning heritage and climate adaptation policies depends on establishing interoperable data systems, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and systematically including cultural heritage within adaptation governance frameworks. These actions would translate the ongoing international policy momentum (expressed through initiatives by UNESCO, UNFCCC, and ICCROM) into practical mechanisms for monitoring, planning, and decision-making across multiple scales.

Limitations and future research directions. This study is based on data indexed in the Web of Science Core Collection, a database that, while comprehensive, may exclude relevant publications from regional or non-English sources. Bibliometric analysis is also limited in its ability to capture publication trends, rather than practical outcomes. Consequently, the results reflect patterns of scholarly activity rather than the full spectrum of applied projects. Future research could expand the dataset by integrating additional databases, such as Scopus or Google Scholar, and by including grey literature, and by using qualitative meta-analysis to complement the quantitative mapping. Further investigation

should focus on how heritage data is integrated operationally into climate adaptation monitoring systems, and on how different analytical scales, including local to transnational, can be aligned through shared indicators and governance mechanisms. Strengthening collaboration between cultural heritage and climate science communities will be crucial in the refinement of these methodologies and the assurance that research findings inform policy and management practices.

While this bibliometric study identifies the predominant research trajectories, it also highlights areas that require further exploration. Few studies explicitly address the integration of local and Indigenous knowledge systems into GIS-based climate analyses, despite their proven relevance for place-specific adaptation and resilience planning. Similarly, while AI and machine learning techniques are being utilised with greater frequency in environmental modelling, their application in cultural heritage risk assessment and monitoring remains limited. The expansion of research in these directions would enhance the capacity of GIS frameworks to capture both quantitative and qualitative dimensions of heritage vulnerability. Furthermore, closer alignment with international mechanisms, such as the World Heritage Convention and its periodic reporting processes, has the potential to enhance the policy relevance of spatial datasets and facilitate more coherent monitoring of heritage under climate stress.

Conclusions

The present study offers three principal contributions that demonstrate the added value of bibliometrics for future work at the intersection of climate change, immovable cultural heritage, and GIS. Firstly, it provides the most comprehensive quantitative mapping to date of this research landscape, showing who is publishing, in which venues and disciplines, and with what thematic emphases. By systematically tracing publication trends, co-occurring keywords, and citation patterns, the analysis unveils the structures that shape the field. These include the strong anchoring in environmental and geoscientific domains, the centrality of risk assessment, and the relatively limited attention to adaptation practice and governance. The findings of the present study provide a foundation of evidence that can guide researchers and funders in the definition of priorities, the formation of consortia, and the positioning of new projects.

Secondly, the bibliometric approach identifies thematic and methodological frontiers that have been under-explored and which are difficult to discern from individual case studies alone. The mapping reveals where important connections are still weak, for example, between GIS-based modelling and local/Indigenous knowledge, between quantitative risk metrics and heritage values, or between spatial datasets and adaptation policy instruments. By highlighting these gaps, the study offers a road map for future research agendas, including the integration of mixed methods, AI-supported analysis, and interoperable heritage-climate data infrastructures.

Thirdly, the work demonstrates how bibliometrics can function as a bridge between scholarship and policy. By aligning its indicators and clusters with emerging international frameworks on heritage and climate adaptation, the study demonstrates how publication evidence can facilitate progress monitoring, reveal disciplinary silos, and support more coherent, cross-sectoral strategies. This approach positions bibliometric analysis not only as a descriptive exercise, but also as a strategic tool for designing research programmes and data systems that strengthen the role of cultural heritage in climate-resilient futures. As future endeavour, we will explore and differentiate between risk-oriented and adaptation-oriented approaches.

Data availability

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new datasets were generated during the current study that is based on bibliometric information on published articles from Web of Science. However, Supplementary Material 1 is available as an Excel file containing eight sheets. First seven sheets (Q1...Q7) correspond to the queries (Q1...Q7 from Table 1) and show all the papers found through the respective query; while the last sheet contains the final 82 papers selected for the current review.

Received: 1 November 2024; Accepted: 12 February 2026;

Published online: 09 March 2026

References

- Aboulnaga M, Abouaiana A, Puma P, Elsharkawy M, Farid M, Gamal S, Lucchi E (2024) Climate change and cultural heritage: a global mapping of the UNESCO thematic indicators in conjunction with advanced technologies for cultural sustainability. *Sustainability*, 16(11), <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16114650>
- Ackland K, Griffiths H, Barker L, Davies S, Driver T, Hunt D (2023) Mapping the impacts of coastal erosion on the heritage assets of Ynys Enlli (Bardsey Island), North Wales, UK. *J Island Coastal Archaeol*, 1–28, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564894.2023.2227944>
- Adaptation GCO (2024) Adapting to the Inevitable: The Global Goal on Adaptation and the Urgency of Action. <https://gca.org/adapting-to-the-inevitable-the-global-goal-on-adaptation-and-the-urgency-of-action/>
- Afroz D (2024) Vulnerability of heritage sites to climatic extreme events: Khalifatabaad ancient mosque. *Int J Conserv Sci* 15(3):1371–1389. <https://doi.org/10.36868/ijcs.2024.03.14>
- Agapiou A, Skarlatos D (2023) Geomatic sensors for heritage documentation: a meta-analysis of the scientific literature. *Heritage* 6(10):6843–6861. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6100357>
- Asăndulescu A, Tencariu FA, Nicu IC (2020) Pars pro toto—remote sensing data for the reconstruction of a rounded chalcolithic site from NE Romania: the case of Ripiceni–Holm settlement (Cucuteni Culture). *Remote Sens* 12(5):887. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12050887>
- Berrang-Ford L, Ford JD, Paterson J (2011) Are we adapting to climate change? *Glob Environ Change* 21(1):25–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.09.012>
- Biesbroek R, Mirbach C, Sietsma A, Garschagen M (2025) Assessment of existing datasets for tracking progress towards the Global Goal on Adaptation (and beyond). *Clim Policy*, 1–15, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2025.2517644>
- Bucci G (2018) Remote sensing and geo-archaeological data: inland water studies for the conservation of underwater cultural heritage in the Ferrara District, Italy. *Remote Sens*, 10(3), <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10030380>
- Cacciotti R, Kaiser A, Sardella A, De Nuntiis P, Drdäcký M, Hanus C, Bonazza A (2021) Climate change-induced disasters and cultural heritage: Optimizing management strategies in Central Europe. *Clim Risk Manag*, 32, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crm.2021.100301>
- Chen C (2005) CiteSpace II: detecting and visualizing emerging trends and transient patterns in scientific literature. *J Am Soc Inf Sci Technol* 57(3):359–377. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.20317>
- Dimitriou E (2022) Precipitation Trends and Flood Hazard Assessment in a Greek World Heritage Site. *Climate*, 10(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli10120194>
- Doyle EEH, Johnston DM, Smith R, Paton D (2019) Communicating model uncertainty for natural hazards: a qualitative systematic thematic review. *Int J Disaster Risk Reduct* 33:449–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2018.10.023>
- Gizzi FT, Sileo M, Biscione M, Danese M, Alvarez de Buergo M (2016) The conservation state of the Sassi of Matera site (Southern Italy) and its correlation with the environmental conditions analysed through spatial analysis techniques. *J Cultural Herit* 17:61–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2015.05.002>
- Gusenbauer M, Haddaway NR (2020) Which academic search systems are suitable for systematic reviews or meta-analyses? Evaluating retrieval qualities of Google Scholar, PubMed, and 26 other resources. *Res Synth Methods* 11(2):181–217. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1378>
- Guzman P, Daly C (2025) Integrating cultural resources and heritage in climate action: a review of nine climate plans. *Environ Sci Policy*, 171, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104127>
- Hategekimana Y, Yu L, Nie Y, Zhu J, Liu F, Guo F (2018) Integration of multi-parametric fuzzy analytic hierarchy process and GIS along the UNESCO World Heritage: a flood hazard index, Mombasa County, Kenya. *Nat Hazards* 92(2):1137–1153. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-018-3244-9>

- Hil G (2019) Better management through measurement: integrating archaeological site features into a GIS-based erosion and sea level rise impact assessment—Blueskin Bay, New Zealand. *J Isl Coast Archaeol* 15(1):104–126. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15564894.2018.1531331>
- Howard AJ, Hancox E, Hanson J, Jackson R (2017) Protecting the historic environment from inland flooding in the UK: some thoughts on current approaches to asset management in the light of planning policy, changing catchment hydrology and climate change. *Historic Environ Policy Pract* 8(2):125–142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17567505.2017.1320855>
- Huang Y (2024) Bibliometric analysis of GIS applications in heritage studies based on Web of Science from 1994 to 2023. *Heritage Sci*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-024-01163-y>
- Hub HR (2024) International co-sponsored meeting on culture, heritage and climate change. Retrieved 14 October 2024 from <https://www.heritageresearch-hub.eu/event/international-co-sponsored-meeting-on-culture-heritage-and-climate-change/>
- Hutton NS, Allen TR (2020) The role of traditional knowledge in coastal adaptation priorities: the Pamunkey Indian Reservation. *Water*, 12(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12123548>
- ICOMOS (2017) 19th General Assembly 2017 - Results and proceedings of the Scientific Symposium. Retrieved 30 September 2024 from <https://www.icomos.org/en/77-articles-en-francais/49783-19th-general-assembly-2017-results-of-the-scientific-symposium>
- ICOMOS (2019) The future of our pasts: engaging cultural heritage in climate action. Outline of climate change and cultural heritage. <https://openarchive.icomos.org/id/eprint/2459>
- Javaid M, Haleem A, Singh RP, Sinha AK (2024) Digital economy to improve the culture of industry 4.0: A study on features, implementation and challenges. *Green Technol Sustain*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2024.100083>
- Jiao Y, Zhao D, Ding Y, Liu Y, Xu Q, Qiu Y, Liu C, Liu Z, Zha Z, Li R (2019) Performance evaluation for four GIS-based models purposed to predict and map landslide susceptibility: a case study at a World Heritage site in Southwest China. *CATENA*, 183. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2019.104221>
- Kapsomenakis J, Douvis C, Poupkou A, Zerefos S, Solomos S, Stavraka T, Melis NS, Kyriakidis E, Kremlis G, Zerefos C (2022) Climate change threats to cultural and natural heritage UNESCO sites in the Mediterranean. *Environ Dev Sustain* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02677-w>
- Kim JW, Kim HG (2021) Landslide susceptibility analysis by type of cultural heritage site using ensemble model: case study of the Chungcheong Region of South Korea. *Sens Mater* 33(11). <https://doi.org/10.18494/sam.2021.3593>
- Kittipongvises S, Phetrak A, Rattanapun P, Brundiars K, Buizer JL, Melnick R (2020) AHP-GIS analysis for flood hazard assessment of the communities nearby the world heritage site on Ayutthaya Island, Thailand. *Int J Disaster Risk Reduction*, 48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101612>
- Kutut V, Lepkova N, Zróbek S (2021) Immovable cultural heritage usage modes: theoretical approach. *Eur Res Stud J*, 1136–1151. <https://doi.org/10.35808/ersj/2092>
- Lei YT, Shen ZF, Tian FS, Yang XW, Wang FT, Pan R, Wang HY, Jiao SH, Kuo WQ (2023) Fire risk level prediction of timber heritage buildings based on entropy and XGBoost. *J Cultural Herit* 63:11–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.06.024>
- Leon JX, Hardcastle J, James R, Albert S, Kereseke J, Woodroffe CD (2015) Supporting local and traditional knowledge with science for adaptation to climate change: lessons learned from participatory three-dimensional modeling in BoeBoe, Solomon Islands. *Coast Manag* 43(4):424–438. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2015.1046808>
- Li W, Jiao J, Qi J, Ma Y (2022) The spatial and temporal differentiation characteristics of cultural heritage in the Yellow River Basin. *PLoS One* 17(6):e0268921. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0268921>
- Li Y, Jia X, Liu Z, Zhao L, Sheng P, Storozum MJ (2022) The potential impact of rising sea levels on China's coastal cultural heritage: a GIS risk assessment. *Antiquity* 96(386):406–421. <https://doi.org/10.15184/aaq.2022.1>
- Liu B, Wu C, Xu W, Shen Y, Tang F (2024) Emerging trends in GIS application on cultural heritage conservation: a review. *Heritage Sci* 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-024-01265-7>
- López-González L, Gomez-Heras M, Otero-Ortiz de Cosca R, Garcia-Morales S, Fort R (2022) Coupling electrical resistivity methods and GIS to evaluate the effect of historic building features on wetting dynamics during wind-driven rain spells. *J Cultural Herit* 58:209–218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2022.10.009>
- López Sánchez M, Tejedor Cabrera A, Linares Gómez Del Pulgar M (2020) Guidelines from the heritage field for the integration of landscape and heritage planning: a systematic literature review. *Lands Urban Planning*, 204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2020.103931>
- Luo L, Liu J, Cigna F, Evans D, Hernandez M, Tapete D, Shadie P, Agapiou A, Elfadaly A, Chen M, Zhu L, Fu B, Yang R, Tariq S, Ouessar M, Lasaponara R, Wang X, Guo H (2023) Space technology: a powerful tool for safeguarding world heritage. *Innovation* 4(3):100420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xinn.2023.100420>
- Nicu IC (2017) Natural hazards – a threat for immovable cultural heritage. A review. *Int J Conserv Sci* 8(3):375–388
- Nicu IC, Fatorić S (2023) Climate change impacts on immovable cultural heritage in polar regions: a systematic bibliometric review. *WIREs Clim Change* 14(3):e822. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.822>
- Nicu IC, Guzman P, Stoleriu CC (2025) Unfreezing the past: near Pan-Svalbard assessment of cryospheric hazards to Arctic cultural heritage. *Sci Total Environ* 1000: 180424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.180424>
- Nicu IC, Rubensdotter L, Stalsberg K, Nau E (2021) Coastal erosion of arctic cultural heritage in danger: a case study from Svalbard, Norway. *Water* 13(6):784. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13060784>
- Nicu IC, Tanyas H, Rubensdotter L, Lombardo L (2022) A glimpse into the northernmost thermo-erosion gullies in Svalbard archipelago and their implications for Arctic cultural heritage. *CATENA* 212: 106105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2022.106105>
- Orr SA, Richards J, Fatorić S (2021) Climate change and cultural heritage: a systematic literature review (2016–2020). *Historic Environ Policy Pract* 12(3–4):434–477. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17567505.2021.1957264>
- Ortiz P, Antunez V, Martín JM, Ortiz R, Vázquez MA, Galán E (2014) Approach to environmental risk analysis for the main monuments in a historical city. *J Cultural Herit* 15(4):432–440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2013.07.009>
- Page MJ, Moher D, McKenzie JE (2022) Introduction to PRISMA 2020 and implications for research synthesis methodologists. *Res Synth Methods* 13:156–163. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1535>
- Pasikowska-Schnass M (2024) The impact of climate change on cultural heritage. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/762282/EPRS_BRI\(2024\)762282_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/762282/EPRS_BRI(2024)762282_EN.pdf)
- Petticrew M, Roberts H (2006) Systematic reviews in the social sciences: a practical guide. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470754887>
- Quamar MM, Al-Ramadan B, Khan K, Shafiullah M, El Ferik S (2023) Advancements and applications of drone-integrated geographic information system technology—a review. *Remote Sens* 15(20). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15205039>
- Quesada-Ganuzza L, Garmendia L, Alvarez I, Roji E (2023) Vulnerability assessment and categorization against heat waves for the Bilbao historic area. *Sustain Cities Soc*, 98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2023.104805>
- Rantanen M, Karpechko AY, Lipponen A, Nordling K, Hyvärinen O, Ruosteenoja K, Vihta T, Laaksonen A (2022) The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979. *Commun Earth Environ* 3:168. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3>
- Ravankhah M, Chlioutakis A, Revez MJ, de Wit R, Argyriou AV, Anwar A, Heeley J, Birkmann J, Sarris A, Žuvela-Aloise M (2020) A multi-hazard platform for cultural heritage at risk: the STORM risk assessment and management tool. *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng* 949:012111. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/949/1/012111>
- Ravankhah M, de Wit R, Argyriou AV, Chlioutakis A, Revez MJ, Birkmann J, Žuvela-Aloise M, Sarris A, Tzigounaki A, Giapitsoglou K (2019) Integrated assessment of natural hazards, including climate change's influences, for cultural heritage sites: the case of the historic centre of Rethymno in Greece. *Int J Disaster Risk Sci* 10(3):343–361. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-019-00235-z>
- Rodriguez-Rosales B, Abreu D, Ortiz R, Becerra J, Cepero-Acan AE, Vazquez MA, Ortiz P (2021) Risk and vulnerability assessment in coastal environments applied to heritage buildings in Havana (Cuba) and Cadiz (Spain). *Sci Total Environ* 750: 141617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141617>
- Ronco P, Gallina V, Torresan S, Zabeo A, Semenzin E, Critto A, Marcomini A (2014) The KULTURisk Regional Risk Assessment methodology for water-related natural hazards – part I: physical–environmental assessment. *Hydro Earth Syst Sci* 18(12):5399–5414. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-18-5399-2014>
- Saha A, Pal SC, Santosh M, Janizadeh S, Chowdhuri I, Norouzi A, Roy P, Chakraborty R (2021) Modelling multi-hazard threats to cultural heritage sites and environmental sustainability: the present and future scenarios. *J Clean Prod*, 320. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128713>
- Salameh M, Touqan B (2023) From heritage to sustainability: the future of the past in the hot arid climate of the UAE. *Buildings*, 13(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13020418>
- Sardella A, Palazzi E, von Hardenberg J, Del Grande C, De Nuntiis P, Sabbioni C, Bonazza A (2020) Risk mapping for the sustainable protection of cultural heritage in extreme changing environments. *Atmosphere*, 11(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11070700>
- Sesana E, Gagnon AS, Ciantelli C, Cassar J, Hughes JJ (2021) Climate change impacts on cultural heritage: a literature review. *WIREs Clim Change*, 12(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.710>
- Tang Y, Liu L, Pan T, Wu Z (2024) A bibliometric analysis of cultural heritage visualisation based on Web of Science from 1998 to 2023: a literature

- overview. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun*, 11(1), <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-024-03567-4>
- Taromideh F, Fazloulou R, Choubin B, Emadi A, Berndtsson R (2022) Urban flood-risk assessment: integration of decision-making and machine learning. *Sustainability*, 14(8), <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084483>
- UNESCO (2023) The operational guidelines for the implementation of the world heritage convention. Retrieved 05 September 2024 from <https://whc.unesco.org/en/guidelines/>
- Usmanov B, Nicu IC, Gainullin I, Khomyakov P (2018) Monitoring and assessing the destruction of archaeological sites from Kuibyshev reservoir coastline, Tatarstan Republic, Russian Federation. A case study. *J Coast Conserv* 22(2):417–429. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-017-0590-9>
- van Eck NJ, Waltman L (2010) Software survey: VOSviewer, a computer program for bibliometric mapping. *Scientometrics* 84(2):523–538. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-009-0146-3>
- Vilcea C, Popescu L, Niță A (2023) Historical buildings and monuments as cultural heritage in situ—perspectives from a medium-sized city. *Heritage* 6(6):4514–4526. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6060239>
- Vlase I, Lahdesmaki T (2023) A bibliometric analysis of cultural heritage research in the humanities: the Web of Science as a tool of knowledge management. *Humanit Soc Sci Commun* 10(1):84. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01582-5>
- Walls M, Hvidberg M, Kleist M, Knudsen P, Mørch P, Egede P, Taylor G, Phillips N, Yamasaki S, Watanabe T (2020) Hydrological instability and archaeological impact in Northwest Greenland: Sudden mass movement events signal new concerns for circumpolar archaeology. *Quaternary Sci Rev*, 248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quascirev.2020.106600>
- Westley K, McNeary R (2015) Assessing the impact of coastal erosion on archaeological sites: a case study from Northern Ireland. *Conserv Manag Archaeol Sites* 16(3):185–211. <https://doi.org/10.1179/1350503315z.00000000082>

Acknowledgements

For ICN and PG this research has been funded by Norwegian Research Council [grant number 351961, SASCHA project], under the European Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Global Change (JPI CH), JPI Climate and Belmont Forum; and by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation funding under Grant Agreement No: 101095253, THETIDA project. AA acknowledges the ARGUS (Non-destructive, scalable, smart monitoring of remote cultural treasures) project (Grant Agreement No.: 101132308) funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. We are also grateful for the constructive comments of the editor and two anonymous reviewers.

Author contributions

ICN: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, resources, software, supervision, visualization, writing - original draft,

writing - review and editing. AA: data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, resources, software, visualization, writing - review and editing. PG: formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, resources, writing - review and editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Ethical approval was not required for this study because it involved a review and analysis of publicly available published literature and did not involve human participants or confidential data.

Informed consent

Informed consent was not required for this study because it did not involve human participants, human data, or identifiable personal information.

Additional information

Supplementary information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-026-06760-9>.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to Ionut Cristi Nicu.

Reprints and permission information is available at <http://www.nature.com/reprints>

Publisher's note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

© The Author(s) 2026